

A STUDY ON CUSTOMER PERCEPTION TOWARDS ORGANIC GREEN PRODUCTS WITH REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE

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Cite This Article: P. Umadevi & Dr. S. Usha, "A Study on Customer Perception towards Organic Green Products With Reference to Coimbatore", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 98-102, 2018.

Abstract:

Organic products assumes essential part in everyday life. The present current world is an integral part of organic products. Buyers are increasingly worried about condition and their wellbeing. In this manner, they are starting to change their propensities for utilization and are requesting greener products whose fabricate has minimal effect on the earth. Green products join green ideas in the assembling and utilize return procedure of these products while enabling the products to meet a similar assembling directions. The study will focus on decision-making factors such as price, availability, food-safety concerns, animal welfare concerns, and environmental impact concerns. The sample will be asked to estimate their average budgets over a period of time that is spent on organic foods. The main objective of the study is that study the reason influencing the consumers in the choice of their green products and to analyze the pattern of purchase with respect to green products. For this purpose a sample of 250 was collected from the respondents who purchase organic products were percentage analysis, chi-square (Kruskal wallis), Weighted average, rank correlation and Anova were used as tools to analyse the data. Hypothesis was framed based on the demographic variables of the study and the factors related to level of acceptance towards organic farming. The conclusion is that there is a relationship between gender and acceptance towards challenges of organic products, marital status and acceptance towards consumption of organic products acceptance towards challenges of organic products and Satisfaction towards organic products. Gender and acceptance towards challenges of organic products and Satisfaction towards organic products. While taking decision factors related to level of acceptance towards organic farming the demographic factors should be taken for decision making process of the study. The variety of products can be increased in future period of time with the shops based on the availability and the requirements of products can be given to persons who are farming organic products so that the volume can be increased with more customer base towards the store.

Key Words: Green Products, Organic Farming & Environmental Impact.

Introduction:

Organic products assumes essential part in everyday life. The present current world is an integral part of organic products. Buyers are increasingly worried about condition and their wellbeing. In this manner, they are starting to change their propensities for utilization and are requesting greener products whose fabricate has minimal effect on the earth. Green products join green ideas in the assembling and utilize return procedure of these products while enabling the products to meet a similar assembling directions. Green products are the products which are feasible, without the utilization of pesticides, made with reused materials and basic bundling. In this way, green customers can be characterized as the individuals who concentrate on the buy and utilization process particularly as it identifies with the creation procedure and the transfer of products, and additionally their effect on the natural condition. In a wide sense, green shoppers mean buyers who have obtained green products and who have endeavored to limit the effect of these products on the earth. It is additionally essential to take note of that the requests of conventional and green markets are very unique. Green promoting has stressed an adjust of value, capacity, cost and comfort with minimal effect of these products on the earth.

Statement of the Problem:

General learning of organic deliver and marking prerequisites can likewise impact purchasing choices among buyers. On the off chance that buyers are uncertain of what the marks really mean, they might settle on choices that were unintended. For instance, the normal purchaser is probably going to see pork marked as "organic" and "regular" as a similar thing. Buyers may likewise accept that organic or normal, on account of meat, implies no hormones and no anti-infection agents.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To know the awareness on green products of consumers.
- ✓ To study the reason influencing the consumers in the choice of their green products.
- ✓ To analyze the pattern of purchase with respect to green products.
- ✓ To know the satisfaction level of consumers regarding green products.
- ✓ To identify the challenges faced while purchasing and consuming the product.

Research Methodology:

Research Design: The design used in the study is descriptive type of research where the researcher has no control over the variables.

Source of Data Collection: To accomplish the objectives of the study, the researcher had to depend on both the primary and secondary data:

Primary Data: In this research the primary data was collected by means of a structured questionnaire.

Secondary Data: Data which have already gone through the process of analysis earlier is referred to as secondary data. The secondary data was collected from the books, journals, published and unpublished reports, company records, website, magazines etc.

Area of Study: The study area is limited to Coimbatore city only.

Sample Size and Design: The sample size of research is 200 respondents, 100 were households working in private and 100 were working in government sector. For the purpose of identifying the respondent's convenience sampling method was followed.

Statistical Tools for Analysis: Percentage analysis, Chi-Square analysis, weighted mean Rank, Kendall's coefficient of concordance, Mean score analysis, Analysis of variance (ANOVA)

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The geographical area of this study is confined to Coimbatore city only.
- ✓ The study period is said to be specific and may not be applicable to any other period.
- ✓ The study is purely based on the views of 200 respondents only and hence the results may not be universally applicable.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Particulars	Frequency	Percent	
Gender	Male	123	49.2
	Female	127	50.8
	Total	250	100.0
Age	20-30	9	3.6
	31-40	111	44.4
	41-50	84	33.6
	50 and above	46	18.4
	Total	250	100.0
Marital Status	Married	244	97.6
	Unmarried	6	2.4
	Total	250	100.0
Educational Qualification	School level	30	12.0
	Graduate	203	81.2
	Post graduate	17	6.8
	Total	250	100.0

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the demographic variable of the respondents were out of 250 respondents 49.2% are male and 50.8% are female. 3.6% are from the age group between 20-30, 44.4% are from the age group between 31-40, 33.6% are from the age group between 41-50 and 18.4% are from the age group above 50. 97.6% are married and 2.4% are unmarried. 12% are from school level, 81.2% are graduates and 6.8% are post graduates.

Rank Correlation for Factors Related to Motives of Organic Product:

Particulars	X	Y	R1	R2	D	D ²
Concern for health	140	21	1	3	-2	4
Concern for status	34	127	3	1	2	4
Concern the environment	10	93	4	2	2	4
To use better quality products	76	9	2	4	-2	4
						16
N = 4					1-R	0.4
					R	0.6

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the correlation of the ranks given based on motives towards organic product. The correlation for the ranks given is at 0.6. it shows that the ranks given are moderately correlated.

The first rank was given to concern for health which reveals that the health consciousness is the motive for purchasing organic product by the respondents.

Comparison between Age and Acceptance and Satisfaction towards Organic Products:

H₀1: There is a significant difference between age and acceptance towards purpose of organic products

H₀2: There is a significant difference between age and acceptance towards consumption of organic products

H₀3: There is a significant difference between age and acceptance towards challenges of organic products

H₀4: There is a significant difference between age and satisfaction towards organic products

Descriptive:

Particulars		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig
Acceptance towards purpose of organic products	20-30	9	1.7778	.57885	2.506	.060
	31-40	111	1.5248	.33702		
	41-50	84	1.4732	.25453		
	50 and above	46	1.5326	.34403		
	Total	250	1.5180	.32727		
Acceptance towards consumption of organic products	20-30	9	2.1267	.16348	14.572	.000
	31-40	111	1.7605	.26889		
	41-50	84	1.6524	.24269		
	50 and above	46	1.6309	.10591		
	Total	250	1.7135	.25325		
Acceptance towards challenges of organic products	20-30	9	1.7889	.23688	5.044	.002
	31-40	111	1.9622	.13688		
	41-50	84	1.9357	.14281		
	50 and above	46	1.9783	.12809		
	Total	250	1.9500	.14514		
Satisfaction towards organic products	20-30	9	2.0444	.13333	6.501	.000
	31-40	111	1.8847	.33308		
	41-50	84	1.7524	.24763		
	50 and above	46	1.9348	.24605		
	Total	250	1.8552	.29561		

Interpretation:

H₀1: There is a significant difference between age and acceptance towards purpose of organic products (0.060) as the level of significance is greater than 0.05.

H₀2: There is no significant difference between age and acceptance towards consumption of organic products as the level of significant is lesser than 0.05 at 0.000. The age group 20-30 (2.12) have a higher impact towards consumption of organic products.

H₀3: There is no significant difference between age and acceptance towards challenges of organic products as the level of significant is lesser than 0.05 at 0.002. The age group above 50 (1.97) have a higher impact towards challenges of organic products

H₀4: There is no significant difference between age and satisfaction towards organic products as the level of significant is lesser than 0.05 at 0.000. The age group between 20-30 (2.04) have a higher impact towards satisfaction with organic products.

Kruskal Wallis Test:

Comparison between Gender and Acceptance and Satisfaction towards Organic Products:

Particulars	Gender	N	Mean Rank
Acceptance towards purpose of organic products	Male	123	118.15
	Female	127	132.61
	Total	250	
Acceptance towards consumption of organic products	Male	123	127.06
	Female	127	123.99
	Total	250	

Acceptance towards challenges of organic products	Male	123	114.33
	Female	127	136.32
	Total	250	
Satisfaction towards organic products	Male	123	116.28
	Female	127	134.43
	Total	250	

Test Statistics ^{a,b}				
	Acceptance towards purpose of organic products	Acceptance towards consumption of organic products	Acceptance towards challenges of organic products	Satisfaction towards organic products
Chi-Square	2.694	.117	6.639	4.310
df	1	1	1	1
Asymp. Sig.	.101	.733	.010	.038
a. Kruskal Wallis Test				
b. Grouping Variable: Gender				

Interpretation:

The above table shows that there is no relationship between gender and Acceptance towards purpose of organic products (0.101), Acceptance towards consumption of organic products (0.733) as the level of significance is greater than 0.05. There is a relationship between gender and acceptance towards challenges of organic products (0.010) and Satisfaction towards organic products (0.038) as the level of significance is lesser than 0.05.

Findings:

- ✓ Most of the respondents are female in our survey.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are from the age group between 31-40.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are married in our survey.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are graduates.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are working with private concerns.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are earning above Rs.75000.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are from nuclear family.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between age and acceptance towards consumption of organic products and it shows that the age group 20-30 have a higher impact towards consumption of organic products.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between age and acceptance towards challenges of organic products and it shows that the age group above 50 have a higher impact towards challenges of organic products.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between age and satisfaction towards organic products it shows that the age group between 20-30 have a higher impact towards satisfaction with organic products.
- ✓ The first rank was given to concern for health which reveals that the health consciousness is the motive for purchasing organic product by the respondents.
- ✓ There is a relationship between marital status and acceptance towards consumption of organic products acceptance towards challenges of organic products and Satisfaction towards organic products.

Suggestions:

- ✓ The variety of products can be increased in future period of time with the shops based on the availability and the requirements of products can be given to persons who are farming organic products so that the volume can be increased with more customer base towards the store.
- ✓ According to advertising efforts and effort endeavors focused at purchasers, organic nourishment makers and advertisers trust so. By investigating the characteristics of the normal sustenance buyer, these organizations and associations hone their showcasing procedures, teaching customers about the potential wellbeing, natural, and way of life benefits organic foods offer.

Conclusion:

The conclusion is that there is a relationship between gender and acceptance towards challenges of organic products, marital status and acceptance towards consumption of organic products acceptance towards challenges of organic products and Satisfaction towards organic products. Gender and acceptance towards challenges of organic products and Satisfaction towards organic products. While taking decision factors related to level of acceptance towards organic farming the demographic factors should be taken for decision making

process of the study. The variety of products can be increased in future period of time with the shops based on the availability and the requirements of products can be given to persons who are farming organic products so that the volume can be increased with more customer base towards the store.

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